

How Communities Mediate the Diffusion of Science: The Case of Granovetters Weak Ties Hypothesis*

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1 Introduction

How do scientists adopt new ideas? This question was high on the agenda of science studies in the 1960s and 1970s. Using primarily survey methods to study the spread of scientific ideas, researchers discovered key dynamics of scientific diffusion. They found, amongst others, that the diffusion of a scientific idea bears similarities with the diffusion of other types of innovation, in that the growth follows an S-shaped curve, just like the growth curve of the adoption of innovations [4, 13]. These studies further uncovered the central role of informal communities, sometimes called invisible colleges [4] or coherent groups [8], in the organization of scientific research. Such communities foster vocabularies and narratives through which researchers interpret scientific findings [5, 3]. Although it opened up a new field of research, science studies of the 1960s and 1970s faced limitations in terms of available data and methods. The explosive development in the availability of data and sophisticated analytical techniques have reinvigorated the field of science studies since the 2000s, allowing researchers to study the development of science at scale [6, 12, 14]. However, such computational analyses tend to focus on the structural properties of scientific networks while leaving the study of the interpretative work that scholarly communities do to ethnographers. As a consequence, our knowledge of how communities adopt and diffuse ideas is fragmented and limited.

This study uses newly available digital datasets and computational techniques to revisit this important long-standing topic. We use citation network analysis, topic modeling and close reading, to study the role that communities play in interpreting scientific ideas as they spread within the academic field. Our case study is the diffusion of Granovetters Strength of Weak Ties hypothesis, first presented in 1973 in *American Journal of Sociology*. We map the community structure of the citation network through which the hypothesis diffuses and examine how different communities develop specific interpretations of Granovetters hypothesis. Our methodological contribution is to develop an approach that bridges the gap between the computational analysis of network properties and the interpretative analysis of meaning (see also [7]). Our substantive contribution is to show that communities reinterpret and adapt ideas as they adopt them.

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2 Case data & network construction

We collect data on publications and scholars referencing Granovetter's 1973 paper from the Web of Science. We use this data to construct a network that represents the diffusion flow of Granovetter's idea as it spreads amongst these scholars. Directed edges are drawn from the new scholars to all previous scholars that they cite when they first adopt, hence representing an influence from the authors of the earlier publication being cited (edge target) to the newly adopting author (edge source). This procedure generates a diffusion network that includes 8,198 publications, 15,056 scholars and 142,227 edges.

3 Diffusion network: communities centered on figureheads

We find that the diffusion network consists of communities of scholars, with relatively many edges between scholars of the same community and relatively few edges between members of different communities. Our comparison with a random network with the same size and degree distribution (directed Havel Hakimi graph) shows that the modularity in the diffusion network (0.623) is significantly higher than would be expected based on chance (p -value <0.001). In other words, scholars who adopt Granovetter's idea do not randomly cite earlier adopters but tend to cite adopters from within their own community; a finding that supports the notion that scientific diffusion is structured by scholarly communities which help mediate the spread of new ideas.

We further see that many communities are centered around some high in-degree scholars, that we term 'figureheads'. Scholars that receive many citations in this network are not simply the ones that move first. In fact, some figureheads that received many citations (such as Albert-László Barabási and Seok-Woo Kwon) first reference Granovetter in 2000, 27 years after the original publication. These figureheads are sometimes cited by scholars of other communities, but are often predominantly and sometimes exclusively cited by scholars of their own community.

So what are these diffusion communities centered on figureheads? Do these diffusion communities embody scientific fields, or research topics?

4 Citation communities are narrative communities

To explore whether these citation network communities are not only network clusters, but also discuss the Strength of Weak ties in a different context, we apply Topic Modeling (LDA) [1] on the abstracts of the largest 12 communities. This reveals that communities use the Strength of Weak Ties in relation to different topics (Chi-squared=2057, df=154, p -value $<0.1^5$), see Figure 2. Communities that are more similar in terms of topics, correspondingly tend to be more connected in the citation network (Pearson correlation=0.23, p -value=0.06).

We further find that the communities are comprised of distinct combinations of scholars from different research fields (Chi-squared=177432451, df=1100, p-value<0.1⁵), see Figure 3. Again, communities that are closer together in terms of research fields also tend to have stronger connections in the citation network (Pearson correlation=0.39, p-value=0.001).

Simply by looking at the topics and disciplinary backgrounds, we can already get quite a good idea of the communities, see Figure 4. Scholars of community 8, for example, appear to be active in the field of communication science and they disproportionately discuss words associated with topic 12, including 'information', 'online' and 'media'. These findings provide prima facie evidence that the diffusion of a novel scientific idea is mediated by scholarly communities with different disciplinary perspectives and research interests. The topic- and research field correlations do not demonstrate that scholars only cite within their research field, nor limit themselves to specialized topics, but serve to show how the diffusion of a novel idea in terms of citations is closely linked to its contextual understanding and applications.

An in depth qualitative analysis of the three largest communities in the diffusion network, which we refer to as *The Organizational Advantage Community*, *The Ego-network Community*, and *The Complex Networks Community*, reveals that the scholars in these three communities hold different interpretations of the Strength of Weak Ties Hypothesis. For example, scholars of *The Complex Networks Community*, mostly physicists, science and technology researchers, and computer scientists, consider weak ties an emergent property of networks that can only be understood by considering and modeling the network as a whole [2, 11]. Amongst these scholars, it is not common to study individuals in isolation and hence weak ties are not thought of as an individual property. For scholars of *The Ego-network Community* in contrast, comprised of predominantly social scientists that use survey data, weak ties are individual attributes. What matters to these scholars, is not the structure of relations in society as a whole, but the relative position of individuals within society [10, 9].

5 Conclusion

Our analyses shows that the Strength of Weak Ties hypothesis not only spread, but also changed. Like a chameleon taking on the colors of its surroundings, weak ties take on a different guise depending on the interests and perspectives of communities of the scholars adopting the idea. This reveals how different communities can use the same reference to make very different points.

This research combined the study of structural properties of the diffusion of science with qualitative methods and understanding. Bridging these two scientific realms allowed to better explain the structural patterns observed and lessen further community fragmentation in the current scientific landscape.

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6 Figures

Fig. 1. The largest 12 communities of the diffusion network in 2017, containing 11,028 scholars and 121,132 edges. The nodes are coloured by their community, and sized by their in degree.

Fig. 2. This Figure shows to what degree communities (rows) write about specific topics (columns). The cell numbers are the average topic coverage of all the articles in the community. The parameters for topic modeling are set to find 15 topics, to discard words that occur in less than 30 articles or in more than 80% of the articles.

Fig. 3. Research area community correlation. Each cell value and color represent the percentage researchers of corresponding research field in this particular community. This Figure only contains research fields for which at least one community has a significant deviation from the overall network (two-sided Z-test) and make up for at least 5% of the community's total scholars.

Community	Size	Figureheads
0	2635	Burt, RS Ghoshal, S Borgatti, SP
1	1687	Lin, N Marsden, PV Wellman, B
2	1306	Barabasi, AL Watts, DJ Saramaki, J
3	823	Uzzi, B Hoang, H Aldrich, H
4	802	Berkman, LF Seeman, TE Glass, TA
5	697	Woolcock, M Narayan, D Bodin, O
6	597	Boorman, SA Goodwin, J Emirbayer, M
7	584	Reinigen, PH Brown, JJ
8	567	Ellison, NB Lampe, C Steinfield, C
9	407	Valente, TW Snijders, TAB
10	359	Maskell, P Bathelt, H Malmberg, A
11	323	Friedkin, NE Kiesler, D

	Dominant Research Fields	Dominant Topics
0	B&E	0 - Organisational Advantage 10 - Entrepreneurship
1	Sociology	2 - Survey Data 13 - Economic Development
2	Physics Science & Tech.	11- Complex Networks 9- Markets & Politics
3	B&E	10 - Entrepreneurship 0 - Organisational Advantage
4	Sociology Public Env. & Occ. Health	2 - Survey Data 13 - Economic Development
5	Env. sciences & Ecology	10 - Entrepreneurship 13 - Economic Development
6	Sociology B&E	9 - Politics & Markets 11- Complex Networks
7	B&E	5 - Methodology 12 - Communication
8	Communication	12 - Communication 9 - Markets & Politics
9	Health Care Sciences	2 - Survey Data 11 - Complex Models
10	B&E Geography	0 - Organisational Advantage 10 Entrepreneurship
11	B&E Computer Science	0 - Organisational Advantage 10 Entrepreneurship

Fig. 4. This Figure shows for each community in the citation network: its size, the figureheads, the most prominent research fields and topics of scholars in this community. We have given names to the topics to capture their essence.